
Impact of Affiliate Marketing on Consumer Behavior Vis-À-Vis Travel and Tourism Industry of Rajasthan

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Abstract Affiliate marketing is a kind of online business in which a third party, the affiliate, receives reward for each visitor provided through hyperlinks on a website or a mobile application. It is analogous to paying a finder's fee for introducing a new or many customers to a company. Flipkart, Amazon, Snapdeal, and more corporations in India have affiliate programmes. To compensate its affiliate partners, companies such as Flipkart, Amazon, and Snapdeal employ the CPA or Cost per Affiliation incentive system. The CPA, also known as the cost per affiliation, cost per order, or cost per purchase, is the amount paid by the advertiser per order. It is used to compare advertising media and vehicles and may also be used to calculate the profitability of a company's Internet marketing. Data on demographics, trust, attitude, indignity, pricing perception, and advertising usefulness were collected for this research utilising a primary data collecting approach using a judgmental sampling procedure and a sample size of 119. The Independent T-test and Chi Square Test are used to analyse the data. According to the findings, affiliate marketing has had a favourable influence on customer behaviour in terms of m-commerce. Even though most consumers dislike seeing adverts in their mobile apps, their acceptance of marketing is growing. Trust, attitude, and advertising utility are all interrelated and play a vital role in shaping client behaviour toward affiliate marketing. Consumer behaviours toward affiliate marketing is also influenced by the consumer's education level, age, gender, and income.

Keywords Affiliate Marketing, Consumer Behavior, Travel and Tourism Industry, Rajasthan

Introduction

The Internet has become critical in the marketing and distribution of tourist services. Increasing tourist demand, reduced distribution costs, better profits, and a bigger market share from the viewpoint of suppliers, as well as convenience of purchase activities and information accessibility from the perspective of consumers, have pushed the widespread use of e-commerce in tourism (Law et al., 2004; Buhalis, 2003). As a result, it was stated that online sales volumes in the United States market surpassed offline sales for the first time (Marketing Vox, 2008). Based on this assumption, tourist companies have adopted a variety of traffic-building strategies in order to attract website users and therefore boost profits. Affiliate marketing (AM) has evolved as one of the most rapidly expanding ways of acquiring consumers and increasing revenue (Fox & Wareham, 2007). It is centered on the concept of advertising another company's services or products in order to earn sales commissions (Goldschmidt et al., 2003). Recent study (Mariussen et al., 2010; Daniele et al., 2009) showed that AM is an important strategic component for client acquisition and revenue creation in the tourist sector.

Internet marketing, often known as online marketing, is a form of marketing that makes use of the Internet to send promotional marketing messages to potential consumers. Email marketing, social media marketing, search

engine marketing, display advertising, and mobile advertising are all part of it. It is made up of many parties, including a publisher, an advertiser, advertising agency, an ad server, and an advertising affiliate. Advertisement is integrated into the online world by the publisher, and the advertiser offers advertisements to be shown on the publisher's content. The ad agency assists in the creation and placement of ad text. The ad server aids in the delivery of the ad and the tracking of data. Affiliate marketing is a kind of internet company in which a third party, the affiliate, gets compensated for each visitor provided via the use of hyperlinks on the website. It is analogous to paying a finder's fee for introducing a new or numerous customers to a company. An affiliate may be paid in a variety of ways. CPC stands for cost per click, CPL stands for cost per lead, CPM stands for cost per thousand, and CPO stands for cost per order. The cost per click (CPC) is the amount paid by the advertiser for each ad click. The cost per lead, or CPL, is the amount paid by the advertiser for each legitimate lead supplied by the publisher. The cost per thousand, often known as CPM, is the amount paid by the advertiser per thousand ad impressions. The CPA, also known as the cost per affiliation, cost per order, or cost per purchase, is the amount paid by the advertiser per order. It is used to compare advertising media and vehicles and may also be used to calculate the profitability of a company's Internet marketing. Affiliate marketing is a kind of internet company in which a third party, the affiliate, gets compensated for each visitor provided via the use of hyperlinks on the website.

Principles of Affiliate Marketing

Affiliate Marketing Fundamentals AM programmes have evolved as one of the fastest growing ways of acquiring consumers and increasing sales on the internet in the context of eMarketing (Mariussen et al., 2010; Fox & Wareham, 2007). As a result, AM is becoming more important in the strategic marketing considerations of companies in general, as well as tourist enterprises in particular (Daniele et al., 2009). Even though exact estimates of the AM market size are difficult to come by, many studies have shown that the worldwide AM industry has been growing steadily in recent years (Cageymedia, 2009; Precision Marketing 2008). AM is described as "the online act of advertising the products and services of others in order to earn commissions on sales leads given" (Hoffmann & Novak, 2000; p.44). It consists of a contract between a company (merchant) and an affiliate, who is paid by the merchant for creating transactions from its customers. In practise, it entails a merchant giving text and/or picture links that affiliates may advertise on their websites if they agree to the suggested terms and conditions. Instead of paying for the placement of the link, the merchant pays a commission on each sale that results from these links (Brear & Barns, 2008; Goldschmidt et al., 2003; Hoffmann & Novak, 2000).

Online Trust

E-commerce in a B2C setting is no longer a novel phenomenon, but knowledge of the broad range of variables that affect transactions between businesses and their customers remains restricted (Koufaris & Hampton-Sousa, 2004). The notion of trust has been recognised as a critical component for effective B2C interactions in the online environment (Grabner-Krauter & Kaluscha 2003), since it has a major impact on customers' online purchasing behaviour (Chen, 2006). It is an essential component in the establishment and maintenance of long-term relationships, and therefore in the development of consumer loyalty (Harris & Goode, 2004). Furthermore, customer trust has been found to lower risk perception (Bart et al., 2005), improve perceived information dependability (Lee & Lin, 2005), and boost desire to promote a website to others (Chen, 2006). Research on online trust in commercial settings has shown a broad range of factors that aid in the building of trust between e-companies and their customers (Corbitt et al., 2003). The notion of trusting beliefs has been extensively utilised to explain the establishment of trust between businesses and their customers (Schlosser et al., 2006). They reflect people' views about the qualities and characteristics of the trusted person, which are required for the development of trust relationships. Several studies in online trust research have attempted to group the wide range of suggested trusting ideas into regularly recurring themes (McKnight et al., 2002; Papadopoulou et al., 2001). Despite minor changes in phrasing, the following groups emerged: Benevolence beliefs (the company prioritises the consumer's interests over its own), integrity beliefs (consumer confidence that the company is committed to agreements, professional standards, and moral principles), and competence beliefs (consumer

confidence in the company's ability and expertise to deliver the promised product! service) Chen (2006) and Wang & Emurian (2005) discovered that the website's interface (physical appearance - i.e. the layout, structure, and content) is critical in generating customer trust. In addition, Basso et al. (2001) emphasised the significance of high-quality visuals for commercial websites in gaining customer confidence. Other research have looked at structural guarantees that reduce customers' uncertainty regarding the trusted party. It was discovered that, while third-party mechanisms such as escrow services and seals of verification have a less significant impact on consumers' decision to trust, community- and reputation-based assurances (e.g., feedback mechanisms) are an important trust-influencing factor for commercial web sites (Pavlou & Gefen, 2004). Finally, a number of studies have claimed that a company's reputation has a substantial impact on the perceived trustworthiness of e-vendors (Koufaris & Hampton Sousa 2004; Jarvenpaa et al., 2000). Other major factors of internet trust are knowledge-based. The notion of knowledge-based trust is founded on the premise that people assess a company's trustworthiness based on their ability to anticipate a company's behaviour and objectives (Koufaris & Hampton Sousa, 2002). Taking this into account, Chen (2006) proposed that the consumer's ability to anticipate may be developed and improved by giving clear information about a company's structure, objectives, and motives. However, there are several possible issues with this technique in the context of AM. Affiliate websites that promote tourist services via suggestion (e.g., content providers or comparison websites) often seek to maximise their profit by increasing sales volumes and earning commission. As a result, completely disclosing their business model may not be desired owing to possible customer concerns about the skewed nature of the services provided. On the other hand, many loyalty and reward websites that split commissions with their customers have a strong incentive in proactively explaining their business model, since customers believe they are being rewarded by doing transactions via these kinds of affiliates. (IAB, 2008).

Tourism and Travel industry

According to the most recent data from the tourism organisation, the United Nations World Tourist Organization (UNWTO), worldwide tourism arrivals increased by 5% in 2013 to almost 1.1 billion, which was more than anticipated (Travel Trade Gazette, 2014:11). According to the UNWTO (2014), global tourist arrivals totaled 1078 million in 2013, with foreign visitors in Sub-Saharan Africa increasing by 5.2 percent to 36 million in 2013, up from 34 million the previous year. Sport tourism is one of the fastest growing industries, adding to these figures (Gibson, 1998; Bull & Weed, 1999; Swart & Bob, 2007; Kruger & Saayman, 2014). The sport tourism sector is expected to expand at a pace of 10 percent to 20 percent each year (Travel Biz Monitor, 2011). Due to the enormous growth and interest in travel focused on human body values such as health and fitness, various organisations have begun to organise sport events and sport tourism packages to incorporate these needs such as physical exercise, sports, and their types of voluntary activity undertaken during vacations (European Travel Commission, 2006; Sylvia- Bobiak & Caldwell, 2006; Eurostat, 2008).

India is ranked fifth among nations, and Rajasthan welcomes one-third of all visitors that visit India, with Jaipur receiving nine out of ten visits; it has the fastest expanding tourism sector. People of all socioeconomic backgrounds, both wealthy and poor, young and old, increasingly devote their free time to sporting activities. India has a sizable sports tourism industry, which is projected to develop at a 30 percent yearly pace, reaching about 9,500 crores by 2015. Sports tourism has a distinct characteristic of all season activities, making it one of the most popular tourist facility suppliers for locals as well as a popular destination for both domestic and international visitors. They go to neighbouring cities and overseas for sporting events. As a result, the research will be critical for both sides' facility providers and visitors.

Rajasthan, a northern Indian state, accounts up more than 10% of the country's total area (342,239 km²). In 2017, more than 475.27 lakh visitors visited Rajasthan, including 16.10 lakh international tourists, in Jaipur, the state capital with a population of 6.89 crores according to the 2011 census. In terms of tourism, the state is very wealthy. It is one of India's most popular tourist attractions, attracting both local and foreign visitors. Rajasthan, with its motto 'Padharo Mahare Desh,' draws visitors for its ancient forts, palaces, art, and culture. However, a new wave of sports tourism has gained traction in the state called Sports Tourism. Tourists go from one end of the globe to the other to engage in games of observation. While cricket is the primary draw for visitors from other nations, "India lags far behind in other sports and tourism," Sports tourism is a multibillion-dollar business

worldwide. According to Cox and Kings, worldwide sports tourism was valued USD 7 billion in 2017. As a capital, Jaipur has a wide range of sports facilities available, including over 30 large sports clubs with facilities for a variety of sports and international events. It also has a broad scope of sports tourism. Cricket field, Pickle ball, Badminton, aquatic sports (swimming pools of international standards), Gymnastic, Golf clubs, Billiards, Gymnastics, and more sports⁶ are available in Jaipur. According to research performed by “TCS Projections” up to the year 2020, the rate of development of domestic tourism is projected to be 7%, while that of international tourists is expected to be 5%.

Table 1: Projected Tourist Growth (number in Crore)

Year	Domestic tourists	foreign Tourists	Total
2000	6.67	0.56	7.23
2005	10.18	0.75	10.93
2010	14.05	0.96	15.01
2020	27.64	1.57	29.21

Secretary, Tourism, Art & Culture, Year 2020

The Rajasthan Tourist Department spends the following amounts on tourism promotion and marketing; however, it does not get enough replies. The table below shows the expenditures on tourist marketing and promotion in the state:

Table 2: Expenditure Spent for Promotion and Marketing of Tourism

Year	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Amount	1905.72	1608.76	915.99	420	236.5	182.06	106.1	498	179.23	114.45

Source: Tourism Annual Report 2012-2013, Department of Tourism, Rajasthan and Times of India

According to the above tables, sporting activities will not only offer entertainment for visitors, but will also assist to prolong their stay in the state and provide many job possibilities for locals. From the perspective of tourist marketing, the different points of view are analysed based on the responses. It is split into sections and analysis for.

Affiliate marketing is associated with Internet-based marketing techniques such as search engine marketing, email marketing, social media and influencer marketing, content marketing, and so on (Olbrich et al., 2019). Affiliate marketing presumes that an affiliate is compensated for each visitor who arrives at an advertiser's website through hyperlinks provided by a third party.

The importance of customers as ultimate decision makers and, therefore, as the deciding element of commercial success is generally recognised in e-commerce research. Because the vacation decision-making process is a complex, multifaceted entity (Choi et al. 2012), it has been approached from a variety of perspectives. The lens of trust has received a lot of attention in this respect. Trust has been recognised as a crucial element in the development of relationships between customers and commercial websites (McKnight, Choudhury, and Kacmar 2002), and as a result, the causes and consequences of trust have been extensively researched (cf. Beldad, de Jong, and Steehouder 2010). Consumer trust in the context of AM, on the other hand, has received less attention. As a result, the purpose of this study is to investigate the factors that influence confidence in travel-related AWs from the perspectives of both customers and AM practitioners.

AM practitioners must consider trust factors while developing AWs in order to win customers' trust and influence a purchasing decision. Competence and integrity are recommended as the most essential trusting assumptions, implying that affiliates should focus on demonstrating these to their clients. In light of this, it is especially essential for content-based affiliates to be cautious with suggestions and to avoid giving the idea that upselling goods is the primary business objective. In this context, the authors recommend limiting cross-selling and pop-up advertisements to a minimum and introducing deep links that take the consumer straight to the merchant's particular product or service. Encouraging consumers to give comments and reviews demonstrates to future visitors that the AW can offer professional assistance. The ability for AWs to access existing customer reviews from the merchant website would improve cross-linking and trustworthiness between the merchant and affiliate sites.

Literature Review

The review on the topic is presented in this chapter as under:

According to Koushik (2021) revealed that Businesses are struggling to comprehend changing client behaviour due to increased digitization and use of social media and Internet technologies. Customers are dissatisfied with inconsistent and unpersonalised service. Digital marketers are experiencing huge alterations in consumer behaviour. Platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram now have the capacity to both build and destroy enterprises. It's currently one of the most critical factors driving user behaviour. Companies must strengthen their social media, content marketing, and PR ties with prospects. With the rise of analytics, businesses can better understand customer trends, buying behaviours, and preferences. Digital marketing has transformed the way a firm attracts and retains customers. This study seeks to understand how digital marketing influences consumer purchase behaviour.

Pillai et al., (2021) showed that, Marketing, like any other firm, has evolved towards digitalization to keep up with the fast-paced environment. Digital marketing nowadays includes techniques like search engine optimization (SEO), search engine marketing (SEM), viral marketing, social media marketing, content marketing, and more. The digitization of marketing channels has made it cheaper, more effective, and more efficient. Due to the global epidemic, people are forced to work online, giving the marketing industry an unexpected boost. Digital marketing has grown rapidly since then and is expected to continue. Also, the epidemic has given its graph a tiny lift. As a consequence, most businesses have turned to digital marketing to reach a larger audience. The research also examines customer perceptions of digital marketing.

According to Abdelhady et al. (2020), Online shoppers have recently been interested in affiliate marketing internet companies. Client loyalty to affiliate marketing websites has been studied. To investigate customer loyalty to travel affiliate marketing websites (booking.com). On the basis of earlier research, this study identifies six basic and supplementary services that impact client loyalty. This study's goal is to identify elements in travel affiliate websites that influence customer loyalty. Using an affiliate website (booking.com) to collect quantitative data is the method used in this research. Statistical analysis is used to verify the seven hypotheses and analyse the results. In both core and additional offers, six components encourage customer loyalty. After analysing the data of customers who used booking.com, the research concluded that customers who used booking.com valued privacy and security more. Customer pleasure affects client perceived value, which affects customer loyalty.

According to Ghosal et al., (2020), Businesses are increasingly directly addressing global customers and exploiting the benefits of the internet channel to gain a competitive advantage as digital technology adoption accelerates. In this case, affiliate marketing is a key e-commerce tactic to increase sales. Affiliate marketing has helped millennials buy online. This study's goal is to analyse the impact of affiliate marketing on millennial views about online shopping. The findings qualitatively examined the benefits of affiliate marketing and their link to perceived ease of use and usefulness. This has boosted people's views towards online shopping. Qualitative research and text analysis of reputable sources confirm a claim. Stakeholders, ecommerce organisations, and entrepreneurs may utilise the findings to grow their present online shopping portal operations using Affiliate Marketing.

Olbrich et al. (2019) analysed how a service business's social media and advertising efforts affect affiliate marketing results. The data comprises 611,081 ad impressions, 15,082 clicks, and 2,672 social media communications over six months. The results of affiliates who utilise social media are contrasted to those who do not. The study adds to the affiliate marketing literature by examining campaign elements such ad media, compensation, relationship length, and corporate focus. It also adds to the multichannel literature by showing that affiliates' microblogging social media activities positively affect ad impressions and, to a lesser extent, affiliate leads. Because affiliates' social media activities impact campaign results, merchants may utilise social media data to get a more complete picture of affiliate activity and success.

Sudha and Sheena (2017) noticed huge upheavals in the clothes retail market. The internet and social media help shoppers find the things they desire. Companies must maintain a strong social media presence or their target audience may just switch suppliers. This study's goal is to examine the fashion industry's use of influencer marketing and the impact of influencers on consumer purchase decisions. **Dwivedi (2017)** Affiliate marketing's

impact on m-commerce consumer behaviour in Delhi NCR. The data show that consumer gender effects trust, attitude, dignity, and price perception. An indignity-advertising utility association was also discovered, as was a statistically significant relationship between attitude and attitude and price perception-advertising utility.

Janssen et al. (2007) studied the impact of affiliate marketing on search engine results and found seven separate affiliate marketing networks. He observed that an increase in the affiliate network correlates with an increase in potential affiliates on the advertising website. The report also stresses the need of increasing the affiliate network to increase the website's SEO and general readership. **Bread and Barnes (2009)** affiliate marketing's influence on the UK financial services industry. Mortgages, credit cards, and vehicle insurance were the main research subjects. Most buyers don't know how to perform good research. Affiliate marketers were able to utilise the credit card section more than others, they discovered.

Fox et al. (2007) highlighted the fundamental rules that must be followed in many affiliate programmes, as well as how online merchants manage the business model and promotional tools that their affiliates may utilise. **Li et al. (2011)** independent of consumption kind, m-commerce experimental characteristics the study concluded that emotion has a substantial effect on customer experience and that utilitarian variables have a negative impact.

Gupta and Vyas (2014) measured adoption of mobile commerce in India. The survey found m-commerce to be user-friendly, safe, and straightforward to use even in remote places. Lack of internet access, language barrier, expertise, and limited number of mobile phone users are some of the difficulties addressed by the authors. **Yasin et al. (2015)** attempted to assess the significance of digital marketing for both marketers and consumers.

According to the findings of the study, even a startup or a small local company may advertise their goods through the Internet. **Prabhu and Satpathy (2015)** investigated affiliate marketing in India and estimated its future potential. The study examined the affiliate marketing technique and the affiliate programmes employed by several e-commerce enterprises. An online job portal was also included in the investigation. The research predicts that affiliate marketing will grow. **Sharma (2015)** discusses the importance of Internet Marketing in e-commerce and gives a summary of it. In addition to CPA, CPL, CPM, and CPI, Internet advertising has many more advantages. The research looked at Flipkart, Snapdeal, Shop clues, Homeshop18, Fashion and you, and deals and you. He thinks Internet Marketing is a must-have for every organisation wanting to grow.

Research Methodology

This study is based on a comprehensive survey that attempts to extract knowledge and information about customer satisfaction from service quality. The survey was undertaken to determine the effect of affiliate marketing on consumer behaviour in relation to m-commerce in India, and it only included respondents from the Delhi NCR area. This study used a conclusive research design and the convenience sampling method. The questionnaire included 21 questions split into six sections: demographics, trust, attitude, indignity, price perception, and advertising usefulness. 152 answers were gathered using the questionnaire technique (on a 5-point Likert scale), of which 35 were discarded because they did not match the target group, or the data was insufficient. As a result, a sample size of 119 was used.

The Chi Squared test is used in the study analysis to examine the connection between trust and gender, attitude and gender, indignity and gender, pricing perception and gender, and advertising utility and consumer gender. Correlation is used to assess the relationship between a consumer's trust, attitude, indignity, advertising utility, and pricing perception.

Objectives of the study are listed below:

- To study about affiliate marketing and it's working with respect to M-commerce.
- To study about various compensation models.
- To study the impact of affiliate marketing on consumer behavior with respect to M-commerce.
- To study the impact of factors affecting affiliate marketing on gender.

Hypothesis Formulation

Hypothesis formulation constitutes the null and alternate hypothesis with respect to each test used in the research.

Independent T-Test is used to measure the difference in the trust, Attitude, Price perception, Perceived indignity, advertisement utility on gender.

Ho: There is significant difference between the variables and gender.

Ha: There is no significant difference between the variables and gender.

Chi-Squared Test is used to measure the relationship between trust, attitude, indignity, price perception, advertisement utility and gender.

Ho: There is no relationship between variables and gender.

Ha: There is relationship between variables and gender.

Correlation is used to measure the correlation between trust and other variables like attitude, indignity, price perception, advertisement utility.

Ho: There is no statistically significant relation between trust and other variables.

Ha: There is statistically significant relation between trust and other variables.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data analysis is presented first in terms of the demographic profile of the respondents as under:

Figure 1: Age

Key Findings revealed that the 76% of the respondents are from age group 18-25 followed by 14% from age group 25-35 and 3% of the respondents are from age group 35-50 with 5% of the respondents are of age group 50 and above.

The gender wise distribution revealed that 68% of the respondents are male followed by 32% of female.

Figure 2: Income

Income wise distribution revealed that the 54% of the respondents have an annual income of less than Rs 50,000 followed by 30% of with an annual income of more than Rs 2,50,000. 7% of the respondents have an annual income between Rs 1,00,000 and Rs 2,50,000 and 9% of the respondents have an annual income between Rs 50,000 and Rs 1,00,000.

Figure 3: Highest Education Level

The qualification wise distribution revealed that the maximum 59% of the respondents are graduates followed by 20% of them are post-graduates, 19% are fresh out of high school and remaining 2% of the respondents have the highest education qualification of 10th.

Figure 4: User Preference

The user preferences revealed that the 30% of the respondents access mobile application only to access e-commerce portals followed by 13% of the respondents uses website only for the same, and 57% of the respondents uses both website and mobile application to access e-commerce portals like amazon, flipkart etc.

Figure 5: Trust Level of User on Advertisement shown on M-commerce

Trust Level of User on Advertisement shown on M-commerce revealed that the 68.93% of the respondents agree to the fact that they can trust advertisement that are shown on m-commerce website or applications, 12.43% of

the respondents have a neutral view; 8.6% of the respondents strongly agree; 8.33% of the respondents disagree and Only 1.7% of the respondents strongly disagree to the fact that they can trust mobile advertisement.

Figure 6: Attitude of Consumers towards affiliate marketing

Attitude of Consumers towards affiliate marketing revealed that 65.5% of the respondents agree to the fact that advertisement gets their attention and have a positive attitude towards advertisement; 9.2% of the respondents strongly agree; 14.1% of the respondents are neutral; 7.7% of the respondents disagree to the fact that advertisement get their attention and have a positive attitude and 3.4% of the respondents strongly disagree to the fact that advertisement get their attention and have a positive attitude towards advertisement.

Figure 12: Impact of advertisement on price

Impact of advertisement on price revealed that the 53.13% of the respondents agree to the fact that advertisement leads to an increase in the price of the goods, 3.16% of the respondents strongly agree; 16.93% of the respondents are neutral, 25.26% of the respondents disagree and 1.43% of the respondents strongly disagree to the fact that advertisement leads to an increase in the price of the goods.

Quantitative Analysis

Independent T-test

Table 1: p-value for independent t-test

Variables	p-value
Trust and age	0.384
Attitude and age	0.005
Indignity and age	0.003
Price perception and age	0.202
Advertisement utility and age	0
Advertisement utility and age	0

Key Finding:

- P-value for **Trust and age** is 0.384. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted while performing independent t-test between trust and age. This shows that there is no significant difference between trust levels of various age groups.

- P-value for **Attitude and age** is 0.005. Thus, alternative hypothesis is accepted while performing independent t-test between attitude and age. This shows that there is significant difference between attitudes of various age groups.
- P-value for **Indignity and age** is 0.003. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted while performing independent t-test between indignity and age. This shows that there is insignificant difference between perceived indignity levels of various age groups.
- P-value for **Price perception and age** is 0.202. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted while performing independent t-test between price perception and age. This shows that there is no significant difference between price perceptions of various age groups.
- P-value for **Advertisement utility and age** is 0.000. Thus, alternative hypothesis is accepted while performing independent t-test between advertisement utility and age. This shows that there is significant difference between perceived advertisement utility of various age groups.

Chi Square Test

Table 2: P-value for Chi square test

Variables	p-value
Trust and gender	0.367
Attitude and gender	0.258
Indignity and gender	0.169
Price perception and gender	0.062
Advertisement utility and gender	0.037

Key Finding:

P-value between **Trust and gender** is 0.367. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted while performing independent t-test between trust and gender. Thus, alternate hypothesis is accepted and that shows that there is no relationship between trust and gender.

P-value between **Attitude and gender** is 0.258. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted while performing independent t-test between attitude and gender. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted and that shows that there is no relationship between attitude and gender.

P-value between **Indignity and gender** is 0.169. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted while performing independent t-test between indignity and gender. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted and that shows that there is no relationship between indignity and gender.

P-value between **Price perception and gender** is 0.062. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted while performing independent t-test between price perception and gender. Thus, null hypothesis is accepted and that shows that there is no relationship between price perception and gender.

P-value between **Advertisement utility and gender** is 0.037. Thus, alternative hypothesis is accepted while performing independent t-test between advertisement utility and gender. Thus, alternative hypothesis is accepted and that shows that there is no relationship between advertisement utility and gender.

Coefficient of correlation

Table 3: Pearson Coefficient and p-value for correlation

Variables	Pearson coefficient	p-value
Trust and Attitude	0.387	0.00
Trust and Indignity	0.091	0.324
Trust and Price perception	0.138	0.133
Trust and Advertisement Utility	0.268	0.003
Attitude and Indignity	0.257	0.005
Attitude and Price perception	0.459	0.00
Attitude and Advertisement utility	0.733	0.00
Indignity and price perception	0.087	0.346
Indignity and Advertisement Utility	0.809	0.00
Price Perception and Advertisement	0.514	0.00

Key Findings:

- The Pearson Coefficient value between trust and attitude is 0.387 and p-value is 0.000. This shows there is a positive, low, and statistically significant relation between trust and attitude.
- The Pearson Coefficient value between trust and indignity is 0.091 and p-value is 0.324. This shows there is a positive, low and statistically insignificant relation between trust and indignity.
- The Pearson Coefficient value between trust and price perception is 0.138 and p-value is 0.133. This shows there is a positive, low and statistically insignificant relations between trust and price perception.
- The Pearson Coefficient value between trust and advertisement utility is 0.268 and p-value is 0.003. This shows there is a positive, low and statistically significant relation between trust and advertisement utility.
- The Pearson Coefficient value between attitude and indignity is 0.257 and p-value is 0.005. This shows there is a positive, low and statistically significant relation between attitude and indignity.
- The Pearson Coefficient value between attitude and price perception is 0.459 and p-value is 0.000. This shows there is a positive, low and statistically significant relation between attitude and price perception.
- The Pearson Coefficient value between attitude and advertisement utility is 0.733 and p-value is 0.000. This shows there is a positive, medium and statistically significant relation between attitude and advertisement utility.
- The Pearson Coefficient value between indignity and price perception is 0.087 and p-value is 0.346. This shows there is a positive, low and statistically insignificant relation between indignity and price perception.
- The Pearson Coefficient value between indignity and advertisement utility is 0.809 and p-value is 0.000. This shows there is a positive, high and statistically significant relation between indignity and advertisement utility.
- The Pearson Coefficient value between trust and attitude is 0.514 and p-value is 0.000. This shows there is a positive, medium and statistically significant relation between price perception and advertisement utility.

Summary Interpretation

The main purpose of the research is to study the impact of affiliate marketing on consumer behavior with respect to m-commerce. Independent t-test was used to measure the reliability of the study. By conducting chi squared test in our study, it was seen that Trust is an important factor and varies with respect to gender and Attitude, indignity and price perception also varies with respect to gender.

With the help of Pearson Correlation Analysis, it is seen that Indignity and Advertisement utility has a positive, high and statistically significant relation, Price perception and advertisement utility as well as attitude and advertisement utility have a positive, medium and statistically significant relation, Trust and attitude, trust and price perception, trust and advertisement utility, attitude and indignity as well as attitude and price perception has a positive, low and statistically significant relation and Trust and indignity, trust and price perception as well as indignity and price perception have a statistically insignificant relation.

Thus, the above study shows that there has been a positive impact of affiliate marketing on consumer behavior with respect to m-commerce.

Conclusion

Affiliate marketing is a form of online business in which a third party i.e. the affiliate is awarded for every visitor it provides with the help of hyperlinks on a website or a mobile application. It is very similar to paying a finder's fee for the introduction of new client or multiple clients to a business. The various companies that offer affiliate programs in India are Flipkart, Amazon, Snapdeal etc. Companies like Flipkart, Amazon, Snapdeal etc. uses CPA or Cost per Affiliation compensation method to reward their affiliate partners. CPA or Cost per affiliation or Cost per order or cost per purchase is the price paid by the advertiser per orders. It is used to make comparison across advertising media and vehicles and can also be used to measure the profitability of a firm's Internet marketing. These affiliates have a pre-defined Commission rate, which are different for different product category. The commission rate of the companies also varies according to the customer. The affiliate partners are paid more in case of a new customer as compared to a repeated customer. Different affiliates offer different

commission rates. Commission rates offered by Flipkart and Amazon are higher as compared to companies like Snapdeal, Infibean etc.

Affiliate marketing has had a positive impact on consumer behavior with respect to m-commerce. Even though, most customers do not like watching advertisement in their mobile applications, their acceptance towards advertisements is increasing. The various factors like trust, attitude and advertisement utility are interdependent on each other and plays an important part in influencing customer behavior towards affiliate marketing. Consumer behavior towards affiliate marketing is also dependent upon education level, age, gender as well as income of the consumers.

Majority of male population are of the belief that there is a need for improvement in the content of the advertisement. However, that is not the case for female population, and they are happy with the content of the advertisement, which are shown to them. The utility of the advertisement is also different for different gender. Each gender has a different view about the utility of the advertisement.

Suggestions

The various methods, which can be used to further improve the acceptance of users towards advertisements, are:

- Use native advertisement as the acceptance level of native advertisement is higher as compared to normal advertisement. The chances of a user clicking on native ad is greater as they are does not break the flow of the website or an app.
- Take user permission before taking users to a different website or to a different application download link.
- Introduce an advertisement free edition to the users. For example, only show ads to users who do not avail the in-app purchase in the application.

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